

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT SCALE FOR TEACHER EDUCATORS

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Abstract

This paper is based on the process of development of organizational commitment scale for teacher educators (OCSTE) and evaluation of its reliability and validity. This scale includes the 33 items to measure the organizational commitment (OC) of teacher educators, which is also covering the three dimensions of organizational commitment. Content validity was evaluated by more than 15 experts from the field of Education and Psychology and for ensuring the construct validity correlation was calculated between the score of each dimension and the total score of the questionnaire. The reliability of the scale was tested by calculating the Cronbach's Alpha and Split half method. For the Item analysis of the scale, index of item discrimination was used and for this item-total correlation was calculated. Only those items were retained which found to have high correlation coefficient.

Key words: Construction, reliability, validity, and organizational commitment

Introduction

This study is highly significant because teacher educators both directly and indirectly build nations and are responsible for nurturing the nation's backbone. The purpose of teacher education has changed from a training process to an instructional strategy to help teachers teach and care for their health. According to NCTE (1998), programmes for preparing teachers will place a far higher emphasis on commitment and competencies. Capable and dedicated teacher educators must be given the space they deserve to carry out the holy duty of training future educators to improve teacher education.

Teachers must give their best effort for their profession every day because they have a lot of responsibility for it (Day, 2004). Teachers who do not feel this emotional connection to their profession are always at risk of burnout in a profession that is getting more and more demanding (Nias, 1996). All effective teaching requires a sense of enthusiasm and

dedication, and these qualities should be considered as characteristics that only some types of educators possess (Day, 2004).

According to this viewpoint, teacher commitment is something that necessitates a close emotional connection to the job. These educators think that a dedicated teacher truly enjoys teaching and is passionate about it. They believe that to be dedicated to their work, they must have an emotional connection to a specific aspect of teaching of teaching.

The study of teacher education is an on-going process that is essential for comprehending teacher educators. Before entering the teaching profession, all candidates must complete teacher education courses. Teacher educators are those who educate others in the field of teacher education. There has long been a neglect of teacher education. It has not received the proper focus or importance. Due to the neglect of teacher education, teacher educators also experience issues with pay, workload, underemployment, lack of access to relevant materials, inadequate physical facilities, subpar library resources, etc., which leaves them greatly dissatisfied. When teacher educators are completely committed to their work, it impacts how well they perform and eventually results in job satisfaction.

Background of the Study

Studies on organisational commitment (OC) have shown that one of the most significant predictors of many favourable organisational outcomes is the maintenance of a high level of organisational commitment. Furthermore, it is generally acknowledged that committed employees put in more effort and go above and beyond to meet organisational goals (Meyer and Allen, 2004).

In recent times, OC has attracted significant attention from both organisational and educational researchers, making it one of the most studied job-related constructs. An increasing amount of research is being done to determine the causes and effects of OC. Many studies have been done in an effort to establish a connection between OC and favourable work outcomes like higher job performance, better attendance, more satisfied staff members, and lower employee turnover (Shore and Martin, 1989). Above all, a current assessment of the literature shows that organisations with committed employees have a considerable competitive advantage and a higher chance of surviving than organisations with less committed workers (Aityan and Gupta, 2012). As a result, it is generally acknowledged that devoted workers are important assets that should be kept in the institutions.

Human resource practitioners defined organisational commitment as an employee's willingness to put in the effort to excel in their role and to help the organisation achieve its

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goals and objectives, as well as the involvement and dedication with which they carry out their work for an organisation. Previous studies and research have shown that a variety of factors, including personal circumstances, personality traits, work environment, management styles, organisational structure, interpersonal relationships, and stakeholder leadership behaviour, have an impact on organisational commitment.

Employees' sense of loyalty and belonging to the organisation they work for is largely determined by other factors, and it can be increased or decreased depending on those factors' presence or absence. OC is a variable that is influenced by a wide range of other factors found in the work environment and organisational practices. An employee's sense of commitment to any institution emerges from their desire to belong to the group, which is typically brought about by a combination of internal and external factors that make them feel the need to maintain membership for a long duration. When the employees are committed to an institution, they empathize with its objectives and want to get involved with it.

Several researchers have defined OC as the sense of belonging to a group or organisation. The level of psychological and emotional attachment that an employee may have to an institution through emotions like happiness, fondness, a sense of belonging, warmth, and affection is known as affective commitment (Jaros et al., 1993). Continuance organisational commitment is the feeling of being bound to any organisation because of the realisation of the financial benefits associated with the job and the high expense of quitting the institution; on the other hand, normative organisational commitment describes a person's loyalty to an organisation because they share its objectives, tasks, and basic principles (Jaros et al., 1993). Similarly, the dedication of a person to the principles and objectives of an organization, alongside their enthusiasm to actively participate in furthering the institution's interests while remaining a part of it, is denoted as value and continuance commitment, correspondingly (Mayer and Schoorman, 1992).

OC was defined by Kanter (1968) as the personal allegiance and devotion that people are willing to show to their organisation. On the other hand, Hall, Schneider, and Nygren (1970) described it as a procedure wherein the objectives of the individual and the organisation become more integrated or coherent.

OC is a person's identity that is tied to an organisation through their mental state or inclination towards it (Sheldon 1971). OC is the employee's connection to the organisation that is characterised by an emotional state, which also affects his decision to stay employed (Meyer and Allen 1997). Rather than being limited to an idea of human relations, *Copyright@2026 Scholarly Research Journal for Humanity Science & English Language*

commitment involves the progress of human energy and an active mind. It speaks of a person's socio-psychological attachment to his group or organisation, its objectives and core values, or his career.

Employees' OC is defined as their eagerness to work very hard for the organisation, a determination to stick with it, and an understanding of its primary goals and fundamental principles (Porter and Lawler, 1968).

O'Reilly, (1989) defined it as "an individual's psychological bond to the organization, including a sense of job involvement, loyalty and belief in the values of the organization."

1.3.1 Components of OC

There are three distinct kinds of organisational commitment served as the basis for Allen and Meyer's (1990) introduction of the three-component model; these forms are emotional connection with the institution, perceived barriers to leaving the institution, and obligation to remain. The three types of commitment are termed affective commitment (AC), continuance commitment (CC) and normative commitment (NC).

Affective Commitment- The approach to organisational commitment that is most widely accepted in the literature views commitment as an emotional connection to the organisation; individuals who exhibit high levels of commitment feel a strong sense of connection, actively involved in organizational endeavour, and derive enjoyment from their affiliation with the organization. Personnel with high organisational identification have stronger psychological ties to their organisation and a greater feeling of being connected there (Lee et al. 2007). Professionals who exhibit high AC remain with the institution because they have a genuine eagerness to stay (Allen and Meyer, 1998). AC and any particular outcome factor, including the target behaviour, have strong correlations (Meyer & Herscovitch, 2001). Organizational-based psychological ownership means an individual's feeling of psychological belonging and affection to the organisation, which includes factors like the organization's reputation, senior management attitudes, tradition, environment, aims and objectives, and institutional rules and regulations (Mayhew et al. 2007). Therefore, to nurture affective commitment, we should direct attention towards professional experiences and task specificity, including freedom of choice, the essence of the job, diverse skills, suggestions, and administrative trustworthiness. These essential factors determine AC (Jaros, 1997).

Normative Commitment - Allen and Meyer (1990) stated that an alternative perspective that is still feasible is to think of commitment as an understanding of responsibility towards the organisation. NC is the idea of being faithful to the organisation (Meyer et al., 2002). It

denotes dedication founded on moral duty to the institution, and individuals exhibiting strong normative commitment continue their association because they think they should be loyal to it (Allen & Meyer, 1998). Situations related to socialisation, like those in the family or society, affect NC (Weiner 1982). Additionally, employees might feel dedicated to their institution for reasons unrelated to socialization, like receiving benefits that elicit reciprocity (Meyer et al. 2002). In this attitude-based approach to commitment, exchange theory plays a role, positing that employees commit to the organization in anticipation of receiving rewards, as noted by Oliver (1990). Thus, NC is understood as embodying a specific form of emotional attachment (Jaros, 1997). Employees characterized by strong NC believe they hold a duty and obligation to persist in their present employment (Aube, 2007). While ACs and NCs demonstrate analogous correlation patterns with precursor, associated, and consequential factors, these relations' strength often differs frequently.

Continuance Commitment - Employees remain with the institution out of necessity, driven by their cognizance of the expenses involved in leaving in CC. The amount or quantity of investments people make and their perception of their limited options are thought to have a significant influence on the CC (Allen & Meyer, 1990). According to Becker (1960), individuals maintain a commitment to organizations for three main reasons: (1) societal expectations emphasize the importance of job stability, viewing frequent job changes negatively; (2) bureaucratic systems may create barriers to leaving, such as financial penalties related to pension funds; (3) personal adaptation to social roles may limit opportunities for alternative positions as individuals conform to the requirements of their current roles. If employees cannot find equivalent benefits in another institution, they are more inclined to develop a stronger bond with their current organization (Lee et al., 2007). The common understanding is that CC is formed as individuals invest in activities or side bets, facing the prospect of losing them if they are bound to stop their participation (Meyer & Herscovitch, 2001).

Objectives of the Study

- ❖ To construct the OCSTE
- ❖ To evaluate the validity of the OCSTE
- ❖ To evaluate the reliability of OCSTE

Methodology

Construction of the questionnaire is a technical aspect of research which is based on the theory of psychometrics. A questionnaire is an instrument with a set of some written items

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with a choice of answers, which is specifically used for a survey or statistical study. In research we have two major types of scales; Likert scale and Thurstone scale which are generally used to collect the personal information from the individuals in a very objective way. In the construction of OCSTE, the investigator has used the five-point Likert scale technique which is a significant method for the development of the attitude scale. **According to Singh(2012)**, Likert scale technique is less difficult than that of Thurston's strategy for Equal-Appearing intervals. He additionally expressed that statements on the Likert scale are worded positively or negatively and subsequently, numerical weights are assigned to them. Subsequently, they are summed to yield a total score. The high total score indicates favorable attitude and low total score indicates unfavorable attitude" (**Singh, 2012, pp.331**).

Sample: The sample of the study consisted of 102 teacher educators which comprised of 51 male and 51 female working in private and government teacher training institutions of Murshidabad district of West Bengal. Simple Random sampling technique was used for selecting the sample for the study. The study was delimited to the teacher educators of private and government teacher training institutions, the study was confined in Murshidabad district only.

Construction and Standardization of OCSTE

3.6.1 OCSTE

To measure the OC of the teacher educators, the researcher found no suitable specific scale for the teacher educators. The investigator thought that it was necessary to develop a specific organizational commitment scale for teacher educators. The first stage of developing scale was acquiring thorough knowledge that offered a profound comprehension of the various aspects of OC. The researcher discussed the dimensions of the tool with the supervisor and other experts after reviewing relevant literature. The investigator chose the following three dimensions based on information gathered from examining relevant literature, talking with the supervisor, and consulting experts:

- i) Affective Commitment
- ii) Continuance Commitment and
- iii) Normative Commitment

Scrutiny and Critique

The researcher considered cultural and contextual appropriateness and relevance for the current study when constructing 87 items that represented both the positive and negative aspects of the areas. A draft containing 87 statements was given to experts in various fields,

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including educational administration, psychology, language, and teacher education. The supervisor's recommendations and specialists' advice were considered while the investigator made several changes to the statements. In the end, 76 statements were selected for the Pre-try out.

3.6.1.2 Pre-Try out

The researcher framed the draft of the 76 items and gave it to 50 teacher educators working in the government and private teacher education institutions in the Murshidabad District. Later, the items that underwent higher rates of rejection and were considered vague by teacher educators were excluded from the final draft of the scale. As a result, the draft of 50 items was formatted for the proper try out.

Table 3.2: Summary of the Organizational Commitment Scale for Pre-Try out

S.No.	Dimensions	PI	NI	Total
1	AC	21	07	28
2	CC	17	07	24
3	NC	16	08	17
Total		54	22	76

3.5.1.3 Proper Try out

The investigator selected 102 teacher educators for the proper try-out. A draft of the organizational commitment scale for teacher educators containing 50 items was administered to 102 teacher educators. After item analysis, 17 items were rejected, and finally, this scale remained 33 items.

Table 3.3: Summary of the OCSTE for Proper Try out

S.No.	Dimensions	PI	NI	Total
1	AC	9	7	16
2	CC	11	6	17
3	NC	10	7	17
Total		30	20	50

Table 3.4: Dimension-wise Description of the OSCTE after Item Analysis

S.No	Dimensions	PI	NI	Total
1	AC	1,2,3,4,5,6	7,8,9,10,11	11
2	CC	12,13,14,15,16	17,18,19,20	09
3	NC	21,22,23,24,25,26,27	28,29,30,31,32,33	13
Total		18	15	33

3.6.1.4 Scoring

Likert Scale Technique was used by the investigator in which five points were given to each

item, i.e. Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U), Disagree (D.), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The researcher opted for this technique because it consumes less time and is easy for the respondents to respond. This scale consists of both negative and positive statements. The score was given for the positive (PI) and negative (NI) items in the following way:

Table 3.5: Scoring of the Items

Category	SA	A	U	D	SD
PI	5	4	3	2	1
NI	1	2	3	4	5

3.6.1.5 Item Analysis

Item analysis is a selection technique that provides a scale characterised by internal consistency. This approach looks for things that will reliably distinguish those found to be high on the attitude continuum from those found to be low. This procedure is used to identify the items found to be valid and appropriate for the scale, dropping or rephrasing the remaining items to serve the intended purpose. Thus, the discriminative power of each item is measured using this method to examine its ability to separate the highs from the lows (Goode & Hatt, 1952). Singh (2006) states that the index of item discrimination is measured using correlation techniques. During this procedure, every item is compared to the internal criteria of the overall score, which is called the item total correlation. Lindquist (1951) called this the "internal-consistency item discrimination index".

The item-total correlation, which is a measure of the item's discriminating power, shows how well the item measures the function that the test is meant to measure. McAlpine (2002) implied that "there are several methods used to calculate the discrimination of items, the most common being the Pearson product-moment correlation between the item and total test score". A coefficient of correlation value below 0.2 is considered as weak, and a value above 0.4 is treated as most desirable (Massey, 1995).

The researcher computed the item total correlation of items using the SPSS-20 version for item analysis. For 50 items, the calculated Cronbach's alpha value was .843. The item-total correlation value determines whether an item is accepted or rejected. The items with an item-total correlation value of above .29 were accepted, and those with a value less than that were removed from the scale. Table 3.7 displays the results of the item total correlation computation for the remaining 33 items.. The scale's reliability increased to (.889) after the items with low item-total correlation were rejected. The final draft includes only 33 items,

and rest of the items were excluded. Statistical software, specifically SPSS version 20, was employed to calculate the data for the current scale.

Table 3.6: Item-Total Correlations for Final Items of OCSTE

Item No.	Coefficient Correlation	Item No.	Coefficient Correlation
1.	0.376	18.	0.356
2.	0.446	19.	0.400
3.	0.428	20.	0.404
4.	0.332	21.	0.414
5.	0.451	22.	0.497
6.	0.536	23.	0.324
7.	0.460	24.	0.429
8.	0.469	25.	0.305
9.	0.461	26.	0.431
10.	0.486	27.	0.483
11.	0.378	28.	0.549
12.	0.472	29.	0.408
13.	0.500	30.	.456
14.	0.468	31.	0.583
15.	0.296	32.	0.392
16.	0.339	33.	0.405
17.	0.400		

3.6.1.6 Reliability

“Reliability is the degree of consistency that the instrument or procedure demonstrates: whatever it is measuring, it does so consistently” (Best & Khan, 2006). A test's reliability refers to how consistently it measures the subject matter that is intended to be measured. The reliability coefficient's value indicates how consistently the test results are generated. Therefore, it offers grounds for considering the score to be reliable and consistent (Garrett, 2009). The researcher employed split half and Cronbach's alpha techniques to examine the scale's reliability.

Cronbach's alpha of a test indicates how the items are related to one another; in other words, it measures to what extent the respondents' responses are interrelated with one another. Lee Cronbach in 1951 developed it as an extension of the Kuder – Richardson Formula (KR20). According to the general guidelines provided by George & Mallery (2001), alpha values should be >0.9 for excellent, >0.8 for good, >0.7 for acceptable, >0.6 for doubtful, >0.5 for poor, and <0.5 for unacceptable. The coefficient of alpha for the present “Organizational Commitment Scale for Teacher Educators” was 0.843, which is good enough to be accepted. “Split-half reliability is a measure of the consistency of the scores obtained from two

equivalent halves of the same test” (Johnson & Christensen, 2012).

Table 3.7: Values of Reliability Co-efficient of the Whole-Scale

Sr. No.	Methods	Values
1.	Cronbach’s alpha	0.843
2.	Split-half Co-efficient	0.788

3.6.1.7 Validity

Validity is a scientific characteristic of a tool that indicates how faithful and truthful a measurement is. It shows to what extent a test correctly measures what it was intended to measure (Lindquist, 1951).

3.6.1.8 Face Validity

It superficially measures something rather than what it actually claims to measure (Singh, 2016). The investigator distributed the questionnaire among the experts in different fields to check the scale’s face validity.

3.6.1.9 Content Validity

It indicates to what extent a test measures the intended content area (Singh, 2016). The supervisor and experts in pertinent fields were consulted to confirm the current scale’s content validity. The experts ensure the high content validity by carefully examining each item to ensure that this scale is specifically related to different aspects of OC.

3.6.1.10 Construct Validity

According to Best and Khan (2006), construct validity is “the degree to which test items and the structure of a test can be accounted for by the explanatory constructs of a sound theory” The researcher examined the construct validity using Pearson's correlation coefficients. The results demonstrated significant relationships between individual dimension scores and the total scale score at the 0.01 level. The result is displayed in Table 3.8.

Table 3.8: Values of each dimension's coefficient correlation with the overall OC score.

Dimensions	A.C	C.C	N.C	O.C.T
A.C	1	0.343**	0.495**	0.781**
C.C		1	0.457**	0.734**
N.C			1	0.847**
O.C.T				1

**Correlation is Significant at the 0.01 level (2- tailed)

AC= Affective Commitment, CC= Continuous Commitment, NC= Normative Commitment

OCT= Organizational Commitment Total

From the above table, it can be said that the correlation coefficient of all the three dimensions is statistically significant and it consequently ensures that all the three dimensions are related to the OC and the scale has the high construct validity far beyond the 0.01 level of the significance.

Figure 3.5: Flow Chart of Tool Development

Use of the OCSTE

The investigator envisioned the following uses of the present questionnaire as it is of immense educational importance for the teacher educators, Administrators, and policy makers.

- ❖ The present scale will help in assessing OC of teacher educators in teacher education programme.
- ❖ It provides an opportunity to measure the OC dimension wise which will assist the teacher educators to enhance their OC accordingly.
- ❖ Administrators, policy maker and teacher educator's curriculum developers may use the present scale to identify the teacher educators with low, average and high OC which in turn provides an opportunity to predict the personal as well as the professional success of the teacher educators in their lives.

Conclusion

The OCSTE has a significant degree of reliability and validity, calculated on the representative sample of teacher educators working in private and government teacher

education institutions of Murshidabad district of Uttar Pradesh, India. The focus of this paper is to develop the OCSTE which will help in diagnosing the status of OC among teacher educators. In this paper attempt was made by the investigator to clarify the concept of OC, as the OC of university teachers is affected by various personal as well as professional demands thus this scale will assist the teachers in analysing their commitment towards the institutions and take the suitable remedies for enhancing their OC.

List of Abbreviations:

OCSTE-	Organizational Commitment Scale for Teacher Educators
OC-	Organizational Commitment
AC-	Affective Commitment
CC-	Continuous Commitment
NC-	Normative Commitment
PI-	Positive Items
NI-	Negative Items
OCT-	Organizational Commitment Total
NCTE-	National Council for Teacher Education
SA-	Strongly Agree,
A-	Agree
U-	Undecided
D-	Disagree
SD-	Strongly Disagree

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